

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Mahmoodian****FIRST NAME: Maryam****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Professor Laurent Cleenewerck****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which answer is correct regarding tables used by the WHO house style?

- If necessary, a column can have blank spaces.
- Any statistically significant notes are listed as the first footnote under the table.¹
- Acknowledgements should be listed at the top of the table, directly under the title.
- The table can be referred to in the text of the article, but this is not necessary.

2. Using US English, which statement is incorrect about the components of grammar in the following sentence?

My friend and I always walk around the quiet neighborhood during our lunch break.

¹ *WHO Style Guide* (World Health Organization, 2004), 33–34.

- There is a compound subject (my friend and I) and one verb (walk).
- There are three adverbs (always, around, and during) and one possessive pronoun (I).²**
- There is a compound subject (my friend and I) and three adverbs (always, around, and during).
- There is a compound subject (my friend and I) and two possessive pronouns (my and our).

3. **Which of these is the correct way to paraphrase the following short paragraph?**

Type 1 diabetes is sometimes referred to as insulin-dependent or juvenile diabetes while Type 2 diabetes is often referred to as adult-onset or noninsulin-dependent. These terms are misnomers because many Type 2 diabetics progress to become dependent on insulin. Furthermore, as pediatric obesity rates have increased, we are seeing more juveniles being diagnosed with the adult-onset type.

- The two types of diabetes are referred to as Type 1 and Type 2. In the past, it was juveniles who were diagnosed with Type 1 diabetes which required insulin. However, since there has been such an increase in pediatric obesity, more younger individuals are being diagnosed with Type 2 diabetes. Also, more adult Type 2 diabetics are becoming dependent on insulin.
- It is becoming more and more difficult to delineate between Type 1 and Type 2 diabetes. We can no longer use terms such as “insulin-dependent” and “adult-onset” to describe the disease. Many Type 2 diabetics become dependent on insulin. Due to the increase in pediatric obesity, many other Type 2 diabetics are juveniles.

² Patrick Sepanek, Dave Kemper, and Steve Meyer, *WriteSource2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*. (Wilmington, MA: Houghton Mifflin Company, 1999), 335–55.

- Insulin-dependent diabetes and juvenile diabetes are both terms that refer to Type 1 diabetes. However, with time, many Type 2 diabetics become dependent on insulin, and because of increased pediatric obesity, not all juvenile diabetics are Type 1.
- There is a clear link between the increase in pediatric obesity and Type 2 diabetes. Now, we can no longer assume that young individuals have Type 1 diabetes, and we can also not assume that adults using insulin do not have Type 2.**³

4. **Which of the following statements is correct regarding US and UK grammar?**

- In UK grammar, acronyms contain periods between the letters (e.g., U.N., N.A.F.T.A.); in US grammar, they do not (e.g., UN, NAFTA)
- In US grammar, acronyms contain periods between the letters; in UK English, they do not.
- In UK grammar, abbreviated titles of people such as a doctor are never followed by a period; therefore, the name that follows them does not need to be capitalized (e.g., Dr smith).
- In both US and UK grammar, acronyms do not contain periods between the letters, and last names of people are always capitalized.**⁴

5. **In US English, which sentence contains incorrect abbreviations?**

- The 2018 award for the best teacher was given to Mr. Jones from St. Mary's Elementary School.

³ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 82-83.

⁴ *University of Oxford Style Guide* (University of Oxford, 2016), 2-16.

- SJCC (St James Community College) named Ms Jones as the professor of the year.⁵**
- Dr. Jones was recognized for his work at the federally qualified health center (FQHC).
- Ms. Jones was honored for her volunteer work at the Jane B. Smith Foundation.

6. **In US English, what spelling, and grammar items are incorrect in the following paragraph?**

On my way home last Thursday I was listening to a radio program called Freakonomics about DNA testing for inherited diseases. They were discussing if having this knowledge affects our lifestyle behaviors; such as motivating us to exercise more or to lose weight. It is difficult to be able to analyze this information because studies can only be based on subjective, not objective, data.

- There should be a comma after the word Thursday, and the word Freakonomics should be italicized and have commas around it.
- There should be a comma after the word Thursday, the word Freakonomics should be in quotation marks, and there should be no semicolon after the word behaviors.
- The word Freakonomics should be italicized, the acronym DNA should be spelled out, and the word affects should be spelled effects.
- There should be a comma after the word Thursday, the word Freakonomics should be italicized, and there should be no semicolon after the word behaviors.⁶**

⁵ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 343-50.

⁶ Patrick Sepranek, Dave Kemper, and Steve Meyer, *WriteSource2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*. (Wilmington, MA: Houghton Mifflin Company), 387-410.

7. **What is the difference between a reference list and a bibliography?**

- A reference list is used for footnotes, and a bibliography is used for endnotes.
- A reference list is used for footnotes and endnotes. A bibliography is used for author-date style citations.
- A reference list is used for author-date style citations, and a bibliography is used for footnotes and endnotes.**⁷
- There is no difference. The two terms are interchangeable.

8. **Which of the following short paragraphs is written correctly according to the Turabian grammar rules?**

- The appalachian area of the US has been one of the hardest hit areas by the nation-wide opioid epidemic. Drug overdoses are now the leading cause of accidental deaths in that region.
- The Appalachian Area of the US has been one of the hardest hit areas by the nationwide opioid epidemic. Drug overdoses are now the leading cause of accidental deaths in that region.
- The Appalachian area of the United States has been one of the hardest hit areas by the nation-wide opioid epidemic; and drug overdoses are now the leading cause of accidental deaths in that region.
- The Appalachian area of the United States has been one of the hardest hit areas by the nationwide opioid epidemic. Drug overdoses are now the leading cause of accidental deaths in that region.**⁸

⁷ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* Ninth Edition. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press), 142-43.

⁸ *Ibid.*, 295-307.

9. **According to Turabian, which of the following is true about a journal article included in a reference list:**

- It is acceptable to use the term “et al.” in the reference list when there are more than two authors. In the text, the terms “and others” should be used.
- The full name of a journal should be written out rather than abbreviated.**⁹
- Depending on the style of a journal article, a reference list can be used for either footnotes or author-date citations.
- An abbreviation is acceptable for a well-known journal. As in: Adams, Ted, et al. “Health Benefits of Gastric Bypass Surgery after 6 Years.” *JAMA*. 308(11), 1122-31.

10. **Which one of the following sentences contains every word spelled correctly according to UK spelling used by the World Health Organization?**

- She was very ill from anemia and needed to see a haematologist.
- She was very ill from anaemia and needed to see a haematologist.**¹⁰
- She was very ill from anemia and needed to see a hematologist.
- She was very ill from anaemia and needed to see a hematologist.

⁹ Kate Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 238–89.

¹⁰ *WHO Style Guide*. (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 63-76.

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